

The Impact of Monetary Policy Instruments on Nigeria's Construction Sector: A Focus on Money Supply, Inflation Rate, Exchange Rate, and Interest Rate.

Jeffery Osayande Guobadia¹, Ndifreke Moses Etim² and Ifiok Ifiok Mfon³

¹ Department of Building University of Uyo, Nigeria. jeff.guobadia@gmail.com

²Department of Urban and Regional Planning, University of Uyo, Nigeria. etim_ndifreke@yahoo.com

³Department of Architecture University of Uyo, Nigeria. ifiokifiokifiok@gmail.com

Received: 12th December, 2023;

Published: 2nd January, 2024.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10450009

Abstract

This research examines how monetary policy instruments impact investment patterns, performance, and sustainable growth in the Nigerian construction sector. Understanding how changes in the economy influence the construction industry's success is crucial since the sector is essential to GDP, employment, and the development of infrastructure. Using information from the Central Bank of Nigeria and the National Bureau of Statistics for the years 2015–2022, the paper examines the relationship between monetary policy instruments and the performance of the building sector. Through correlation and regression analyses, the research unveils the pivotal role of monetary factors, especially money supply, in shaping various economic indicators. Strong positive correlations with inflation rate, interest rate, and exchange rate were established underscoring the intricate ties between monetary policy and key elements influencing the construction industry. The multifaceted recommendations presented for the Nigerian construction sector aim to cultivate growth, stability, and transparency.

Keywords: Monetary Policy Instruments, Construction Sector, Nigeria, Money Supply, Inflation Rates, Interest Rates, Exchange Rates,

1.0 Introduction

The convergency of economic prosperity is a function of the health of national economies mostly enhanced by the contributions of its different sectors. The Nigerian economy for instance, as do other economies globally, is shaped by monetary policy fluctuations, which aim to guide the nation towards prosperity (Rui et al., 2019). These fluctuations can affect various sectors, ranging from stability to significant opportunities, especially the construction sector. The intricate link between monetary policy instruments and industrial performance is best shown by the construction sector, which is a major actor in the economy, particularly due to its visible structures which is somewhat seen as a form of national development (Smets, 2018). This study examines many monetary policy factors in connection to the construction sector, including the dynamics of money supply, inflation, exchange rate volatility, and interest rate volatility. It aims to understand the profound influence these policy

instruments have on the construction sector's core, from individual projects to investment decisions and overall industry performance.

Monetary policy is crucial in under-developed countries like Nigeria, as it helps achieve economic objectives such as employment, growth, balance of payment equilibrium, and stable general price levels (Nwoko et al., 2016). It promotes economic development and equilibrium in all aspects of the economy, including the construction industry. The construction industry is essential for the economy, as it provides physical constructed facilities for other activities (Baghebo and Stephen, 2014). The construction industry's gross output is the total monetary worth of all the buildings and civil engineering projects produced in a specific time period (Olanrewaju et al., 2015). One of Nigeria's main sectors, the construction sector, has over time aided in the expansion of the nation as a whole. It is impossible to overstate the significance of the building sector, as it is the only one that the public can see actively developing in a nation (Isa et al., 2013).

With a major impact on a nation's growth, the construction industry is an important sector in both established and developing nations. With the help of yearly capital budgetary provisions, Nigeria's public sector is a significant source of funding for expansion (Iheanacho, 2016). The National Planning Commission (NPC) reported that the construction sector in Nigeria experienced a 12.09% growth in 2010, compared to 11.97% in 2009. Major projects that contributed to this growth include national road rehabilitation, Presidential Initiative Projects, PPP projects, housing unit types, River Niger dredging, and railway lines. The nominal value of construction activities increased to ₦456.04 billion in 2011, and the sector's share of GDP growth improved from 2.86% in 2010 to 3.22% in 2011 (Akinseinde and Awolesi, 2015).

These goals of monetary policy remain the same irrespective of the package of instruments in use. It attempts at maintaining a balance as possible between the supply and demand for the monetary assets of the economy in order to achieve adequate economic growth (Borio, 2014). This broad purpose may be transmitted or rather translated into several specific objectives such as price stability, high level of employment or an acceptable growth rate of the real gross domestic product (GDP), as well as balance of payment equilibrium (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2013). This study intends to explore the relationship between monetary policy tools and their impact on Nigeria's construction sector and will examine four key monetary policy instruments: money supply, inflation, exchange rates, and interest rates. The study will examine how these instruments affect the performance of the construction sector as well as examine how these instruments shape construction project initiation, progress, completion, investment decisions, technology adoption, market expansion, and industry metrics like revenue growth, profit margins, and employment. The study will be limited to construction sector data from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and the National Bureau of Statistics between 2015 and 2022. The methodological approach will integrate quantitative method and a scoping review, ensuring a thorough and well-documented rationale for the study.

2.0 Literature Review

Nigeria's monetary policy framework has evolved to adapt to changing economic conditions and align with national development goals, contributed to by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) (Obioma and Onyebueke, 2018). The CBN, being the primary monetary authority responsible for policy formulation and implementation in the country, enhances policy development through structures within it such as the Monetary Policy

Committee (MPC) (Bassey and Essien, 2014). The MPC, which convenes bi-annually to set policy rates and guidelines, with support from the Monetary Policy Department (MPD), utilises frameworks that consist of distinct components aimed at achieving specific objectives and utilizing various instruments to execute policy decisions (Uwatt et al., 2018). Nigeria's monetary policy, an offshoot of the results of MPC, focuses on price stability, maintaining a low and stable inflation rate since the early 2000s, and fostering exchange rate stability for the Naira. The approach has evolved through various political and statutory regimes in the country and within the CBN, from fixed to managed and flexible frameworks (Nwoko, Ihemeje and Anumadu, 2016). The goal, as inclined by Anowor and Okorie (2016), has been to safeguard the financial system's stability to support economic growth and development, emphasizing resilience and soundness. Instruments used to achieve these objectives, according to Ejem, Ogbonna and Ogbudu (2020), include the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), the Cash Reserve Requirement (CRR), and Open Market Operations (OMOs), among others. However, despite the inputs and efforts by the MPC in line with the above frameworks, challenges persist particularly in strengthening the Naira, including vulnerability to global economic shocks, the need for coherent fiscal policy coordination, and the complexity of implementing policies in Nigeria's informal sector, all of which somewhat have effects on the performance of construction sector particularly with budgetary allocation to the sector from the yearly national budgets (Alley, 2018).

2.1 Overview of Construction Sector Growth

Isa et al. (2013) opined that organized construction contracting in Nigeria began in the 1940s with few foreign companies coming into operation. The oil boom of the 1970s which was bolstered by Nigeria's Independence in 1960 brought an upward trend in the construction activities and up to the end of the second Republic in 1983, the construction industry in Nigeria has witnessed an overwhelming upsurge in construction contracting dominated by expatriate companies with few indigenous companies (Afinotan and Ojakorotu, 2014). Unfortunately, the period also exposed the country's indigenous companies' low level of human resources development required for; planning, designing, constructing and maintaining the magnitude (in size and number) of projects conceived by the government. However, with improved training institutions, engagement of expatriates, collaborations between indigenous and foreign entrepreneurs, political stability and improved government policies, and the apparent resources gap needed for successful completion of complex projects between indigenous companies and their foreign counterparts are now closer compared to the pre-independence era (Isa et al., 2013, Mfon and Etim, 2023).

The construction sector has grown over the years, as a result of demands for real estate, housing, and the provision of infrastructure to support an increasing population size, the need to open up communities to foster inter-state and inter-regional trade and movement (NBS, 2015). This has seen the active involvement of all stakeholders in the success of the industry. However, the major client of the sector, the government, interacts with the industry majorly as regulators, purchasers and financiers (NBS, 2015). The economy of Nigeria increased 3.23 percent quarter-on-quarter in the second quarter of 2017, recovering from a 13.3 percent contraction in the first quarter. GDP Growth Rate in Nigeria averaged 1.17 percent from 2010 until 2017, reaching an all-time high of 10.59 percent in the third quarter of 2010 and a record low of -13.98 percent in the first quarter of 2016 (CBN, 2017).

Figure 2.1: Nigeria GDP from Construction (Trading Economics, 2023)

Figure 2.2. Nigeria GDP Annual Growth Rate (Trading Economics, 2023)

2.2 Theoretical Framework: New Keynesian Framework

The New Keynesian framework is a valuable tool for analyzing the impact of monetary policy on Nigeria's construction sector and guiding policies towards sustainable growth. It highlights nominal and real rigidities, offering insights into deploying monetary tools to encourage sustainable construction practices (Idris, 2019). The framework acknowledges price stickiness in the construction sector, particularly in materials and labour costs, as well as targeted monetary policy interventions which could incentivize sustainable technologies and materials, even at higher initial costs (Rostagno et al., 2019). As suggested by (Galí, 2015), effective communication and forward guidance can guide investment decisions towards long-term sustainability objectives. More so, Antal and Bergh (2013), inclined that monetary policy adjustments, like interest rate changes, can significantly influence aggregate demand, presenting an opportunity for tailored fiscal and monetary packages to stimulate demand for green buildings and sustainable infrastructure projects. Addressing credit market imperfections through central bank programmes, which is wholly supported by this theory, has the potency of mitigating information asymmetries and risk aversion, ensuring increased access to finance for sustainable construction endeavours.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Influence of Monetary and Fiscal Policies on Construction Output Levels in Kenya

Mbusi (2016) categorized the factors that influence construction output levels in Kenya as Monetary and Fiscal Policies. He stated that the factors that fall under the Monetary Policy category are Exchange, Inflation and Interest rates while the factors that fall under the Fiscal Policy category are Government spending, Tax rate and Tax on goods. However, the following was deduced from the study.

Figure 2.3. Conceptual Framework (Mbusi, 2016)

2.3.2 The Impact of Monetary Policy on the Economic Growth of Nigeria

This study showed that monetary policy is maintained through actions such as increasing interest rate, or changing the amount of money banks need to keep in vault. According to De Fiore et al. (2018) three basic kinds of monetary policy decision can be made - the amount of money in circulation; the level of interest rate; and the functions of credit markets and the banking system. The combination of these measures is designed to regulate the value, supply and cost of money in an economy, in line with the level of economic activity (Bernanke, 2020). A close observation of the above shows that monetary policy boils down to adjusting the supply of money in the economy to achieve some combination of inflation and output stabilization. Most economist agree that in the long run output usually measured by gross domestic product (GDP) is fixed, so any changes in the money supply only cause prices to change (Nwoko et al., 2016). However, in the short-run, because prices and wages usually do not adjust immediately, changes in money supply can affect the actual production of goods and services (Koshy, 2013).

Figure 2.4. Conceptual framework (Nwoko et al., 2016).

2.5 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework outlines the factors that determine how monetary policies affect the performance of the construction sector.

Figure 2.5. Conceptual Framework of the Study (Researcher, 2023)

The construction sector in Nigeria relies heavily on monetary policies for growth and development, which is influenced by factors such as Money Supply, Inflation Rate, Exchange Rate, and Interest Rate, as indicated above. High money supply can provide liquidity, but excessive supply can lead to inflation and project viability (Agénor and Silva, 2013). As stated by Alshboul et al. (2022), stable inflation promotes predictability, while high inflation introduces uncertainties, thus negatively impacting the expected growth of the construction sector. A stable exchange rate, also, enhances efficiency, but devaluation, on the other hand, raises import costs and affects profit margins (Auboin and Ruta, 2013). Furthermore, lower interest rates incentivize borrowing, but high rates limit access to finance, hindering investment. Understanding these interactions is crucial for designing effective policies that drive sustainable growth in the construction sector.

Monetary Policy no doubt, is a deliberate economic strategy taken to influence the economy by the government through the Central Bank of Nigeria. The Central Bank on its part is saddled with the responsibility of making salient policies that would give a positive drive to the economy, hence the need to provide salient techniques and tools to achieve this mandate (Juhro, 2022). It attempts at maintaining a balance as possible between the supply and demand for the monetary assets of the economy in order to achieve adequate economic growth. This broad purpose may be transmitted or rather translated into several specific objectives such as price stability, high level of employment or an acceptable growth rate of the real gross domestic product (GDP), as well as balance of payment equilibrium (Nwoko et al., 2016). The construction sector being one of the sectors in Nigeria is said to be the visible sign of development of any administration. In recent times, the growth of this sector has been

inconsistent with different political administrations of the country (Olutuase, 2014). This has left stakeholders in dismay as to how to plan for the growth of this sector. With the emergence of various economic policies from the Central Bank, one would find it difficult in discerning on the right one to use to effectively plan for the growth of this sector (Afolabi et al., 2019). The study provides stakeholders with the information on how monetary policies operate, particularly in view of monetary instruments such as money supply, inflation rate, exchange rate, and interest rate

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Study Area

Nigeria was the research area for this study. Nigeria consists of thirty-six (36) states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Its administrative capital is the FCT while the commercial capital is Lagos State. Though, it is composed of different sectors, which are divided into the primary and secondary categories, the main source of revenue, according to Falola and Agbo (2019), is from the sale of crude oil. The weak nature of the Nigerian economy dated back to independence in 1960 which up till now, depends on external sources for most of its needs as a country (Adebanwi and Obadare, 2013). These significantly affect the primary production activities in the primary sectors (agricultural sector, mining and quarrying sector as well as the oil and gas sector) which accounts for 65% of the nation's GDP and 80% of revenues from the government (NBS, 2011). The construction sector among other sectors which makes up the secondary category of the economy only makes 2% of gross output (Isa *et al.*, 2013). In spite of the efforts of substantive political administrations to encourage the development of new sectors (telecommunication, power, etc.), there has not been a commensurable growth in employment nor is their reduction in the poverty level of the nation's citizens. The geometric increase in security challenges in the country, lack of sustainable economic policies has hampered growth rate in various sectors of the economy (Enweremadu, 2013). This research touches on the country's monetary policies as it affects one of its major sectors, the construction sector.

3.2 Research Design

A quantitative strategy, a scoping review, and a secondary research technique will be employed in the study (Maida et al., 2022). In order to investigate the impact of monetary policy tools on Nigeria's construction industry, the technique entails gathering and evaluating numerical data from sources of current literature, the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics, as well as the Central Bank of Nigeria. By offering actual data and statistical insights into their effects, the research seeks to disentangle the intricate relationships between the money supply, inflation rate, exchange rate, and interest rate within the construction sector. This methodical approach facilitates a thorough examination of the quantitative data that is accessible, leading to a more profound comprehension of the ways in which these monetary policy tools influence the dynamics of Nigeria's building sector. This study adopted secondary data collection strategy. The data was sourced from previous researches, Central Bank of Nigeria (C.B.N.) and the National Bureau of Statistics (N.B.S.) from 2010 – 2017. The data sourced are as follows:

1. Inflation rates, exchange rates, and interest rates between 2015 and 2022 in Nigeria.

2. Budgetary allocation to the construction sector between 2015 and 2022
3. Economic contribution of the construction industry to Nigerian economy

4.0 Data Presentation and Analysis of Findings

Table 4.1 3-Year Moving Average of Money Supply, Inflation Rates, Interest Rates, Exchange Rates, and Percentage Contribution of the Construction Sector to Nigeria GDP.

Year	Money Supply	Inflation Rates	Interest Rates	Exchange Rates	% Contribution of the Construction Sector to GDP
2015	-	-	-	-	-
2016	344.5233	13.7367	8.7	250.5733	0.5833
2017	564.5433	14.7667	6.2	288.4533	0.09
2018	554.9	13.3333	5.4667	306.2633	2.8167
2019	475.5167	12.2500	5.3333	323.9367	0.8
2020	367.4333	13.8667	3.7	355.6267	2.39
2021	385.4133	16.3500	2.5	395.3133	4.6867
2022	-	-	-	-	-

(Source: CBN, NBS, Researcher's compilation)

Table 4.2: Pearson Product Correlation analysis among monetary policy instruments of money supply, inflation rates, interest rates, and exchange rates, and the percentage contribution of the construction sector to Nigeria's GDP from 2015 to 2022

Correlations

	Money Supplied	Inflation Rate	Interest Rate	Exchange Rate	Contributon to GDP
Pearson Correlation	1	.902**	.766*	.871**	.395
Money Supplied Sig. (2-tailed)		.002	.027	.005	.333
N	8	8	8	8	8
Pearson Correlation	.902**	1	.746*	.969**	.590
Inflation Rate Sig. (2-tailed)	.002		.034	.000	.123
N	8	8	8	8	8
Pearson Correlation	.766*	.746*	1	.612	.015
Interest Rate Sig. (2-tailed)	.027	.034		.107	.973
N	8	8	8	8	8
Pearson Correlation	.871**	.969**	.612	1	.687
Exchange Rate Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.000	.107		.060
N	8	8	8	8	8
Pearson Correlation	.395	.590	.015	.687	1
Contributon to C					
LE Sig. (2-tailed)	.333	.123	.973	.060	
P					
N	8	8	8	8	8

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation results reveal significant relationships among the variables. "Money Supplied" has a strong positive correlation with "Inflation Rate" ($r = 0.902$, $p = 0.002$) and a moderately strong positive correlation with "Interest Rate" ($r = 0.766$, $p = 0.027$) and "Exchange Rate" ($r = 0.871$, $p = 0.005$). However, its correlation with "Contribution to GDP" is weaker and not statistically significant ($r = 0.395$, $p = 0.333$). The findings suggest that "Money Supplied" is closely related to economic indicators such as "Inflation Rate," "Interest Rate," and "Exchange Rate," but its connection with "Contribution to GDP" is less pronounced and lacks statistical significance in this dataset.

These correlation results provide valuable insights into the relationships between key economic variables. Money Supplied exhibits a strong positive correlation with inflation rate, suggesting that as the money supply increases, there is a tendency for inflation to rise. This could have implications for construction costs and pricing within the industry, impacting the overall economic environment. The moderately strong positive correlation between money supplied and interest rate implies a connection between monetary policy and interest rates. In the construction sector, changes in interest rates can influence borrowing costs for projects and, consequently, the level of construction activity. This correlation highlights the importance of monitoring monetary policy decisions for stakeholders in the Nigerian construction industry. Similarly, the positive correlation between money supplied and exchange rate suggests a relationship between the money supply and the value of the local currency. In the construction industry, fluctuations in exchange rates can impact the costs of imported materials and affect the overall cost structure of construction projects. However, the weaker and statistically insignificant correlation between "Money allocated to the sub sector and its contribution to GDP" indicates that while money supply may be closely linked to certain economic indicators, its relationship with the overall contribution of the construction industry to the national GDP is less clear. This could be due to various factors such as the specific dynamics of the construction sector, government policies, or corruption.

4.2 The Impact of Monetary Policy on Construction Sector Performance

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.404	1.137		.355	.735
	Money Supplied	.003	.003	.395	1.052	.333

a. Dependent Variable: Contribution to GDP

Source: SPSS Extract.

The regression analysis investigates the relationship between the dependent variable, "Contribution to GDP," and the independent variable, "Money Supplied." The intercept (constant) is 0.404, suggesting that when Money Supplied is zero, the Contribution to GDP is expected to be approximately 0.404. The coefficient for Money Supplied is 0.003, indicating that for a one-unit increase in Money Supplied, the Contribution to GDP is

expected to increase by 0.003 units. The standardized coefficient (Beta) for Money Supplied is 0.395, providing a measure of its contribution to the standardized prediction of Contribution to GDP. However, the results are not statistically significant at the conventional 0.05 significance level, as both the intercept and Money Supplied have p-values above 0.05.

Inflation Rates.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-.188	1.041		-.180	.863
Inflation Rate	.153	.085	.590	1.792	.123

a. Dependent Variable: Contribution to GDP

Source: SPSS Extract.

The regression analysis examines the relationship between the dependent variable, "Contribution to GDP," and the independent variable, "Inflation Rate." The intercept (constant) is -0.188, indicating that when the Inflation Rate is zero, the Contribution to GDP is expected to be approximately -0.188. The coefficient for Inflation Rate is 0.153, suggesting that for a one-unit increase in the Inflation Rate, the Contribution to GDP is expected to increase by 0.153 units. The standardized coefficient (Beta) for Inflation Rate is 0.590, reflecting its contribution to the standardized prediction of Contribution to GDP. However, the results are not statistically significant at the conventional 0.05 significance level, as both the intercept and Inflation Rate have p-values above 0.05 (0.863 and 0.123, respectively).

Interest Rate

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.388	1.121		1.238	.262
Interest Rate	.008	.229	.015	.036	.973

a. Dependent Variable: Contribution to GDP

Source: SPSS Extract.

The regression analysis explores the relationship between the dependent variable, "Contribution to GDP," and the independent variable, "Interest Rate." The intercept is 1.388, indicating that when the Interest Rate is zero, the Contribution to GDP is around 1.388. However, both the intercept and the Interest Rate coefficient lack statistical significance, with p-values of 0.262 and 0.973, respectively. The insignificant p-values suggest that

the observed results could likely occur due to random chance, questioning the practical significance of the Interest Rate's impact on Contribution to GDP.

Exchange Rate

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-.407	.920		-.442	.674
Exchange Rate	.008	.003	.687	2.317	.060

a. Dependent Variable: Contribution to GDP.

Source: SPSS Extract.

The regression analysis examines the relationship between the dependent variable, "Contribution to GDP," and the independent variable, "Exchange Rate." The intercept is -0.407, indicating that when the Exchange Rate is zero, the Contribution to GDP is around -0.407, but this is not statistically significant (p-value = 0.674). The Exchange Rate coefficient is 0.008, suggesting that a one-unit increase in the Exchange Rate corresponds to a 0.008 unit increase in Contribution to GDP. The standardized coefficient (Beta) is 0.687, indicating a moderate contribution of the Exchange Rate to the standardized prediction of Contribution to GDP. However, the p-value for the Exchange Rate is marginally significant at 0.060.

6.0 Conclusion

The study explored the impact of monetary policy instruments on the construction sector in Nigeria, a significant part of the country's GDP. From the correlation and regression analyses it becomes evident that monetary factors, particularly money supplied play a substantial role in influencing various economic indicators. Notably, the strong positive correlations with inflation rate, interest rate and exchange rate underscore the inter-connectedness of monetary policy with key elements impacting the construction industry. However, the absence of a statistically significant correlation between money supplied and the Contribution to GDP within the construction sector raises pertinent questions. This inconclusiveness may be attributed to specific challenges inherent to the Nigerian construction industry, including nuanced regulatory frameworks, government policies, and potentially systemic issues like corruption.

The recommendations put forth for the Nigerian construction sector are multifaceted, focusing on diverse aspects to foster growth, stability, and transparency within the industry. Firstly, policymakers are urged to diversify monetary policies, tailoring strategies to specifically address challenges unique to the construction sector. This approach recognizes the need for industry-specific monetary framework that can better support the sector's development and resilience. Stakeholders in the sector should intensify their monitoring of inflation rates and interest rates. This heightened vigilance is crucial as these variables exhibit significant correlations with money supply. By closely tracking changes in these rates, industry participants can adapt to evolving

economic conditions, thereby mitigating potential challenges and strategically leveraging emerging opportunities for sustainable growth.

Another key recommendation involves the implementation of effective risk management strategies to navigate exchange rate fluctuations. Given the positive correlation between "Money Supplied" and "Exchange Rate," industry players are encouraged to hedge against currency risks. This proactive risk management approach is particularly relevant for mitigating the potential impact of currency fluctuations on the cost structure of construction projects, ensuring financial stability and project viability. The call for enhancing transparency and implementing robust anti-corruption measures within the construction sector forms a crucial pillar of this recommendation. Clearer regulations and ethical business practices are proposed to create an environment conducive to increased investment. By fostering transparency, stakeholders can not only attract more investment but also contribute to a more accurate assessment of the construction industry's actual contribution to the national GDP, thereby supporting evidence-based policy decisions.

References

- Abdullahi, M. and Bala, K. (2018) Analysis of the Causality Links between the Growth of the Construction Industry and the Growth of the Nigerian Economy. *Journal of Construction in Developing Countries*, 23(1), pp.103-113.
- Abdullahi, S.I., Shehu, K.K., Shuaibu, M., Saleh, S.G. and Usman, M.D. (2021) Monetary Variables, Economic Growth and Monetary Policy in Nigeria. *Journal of Advanced Studies in Finance*, 12(2), pp.115-125.
- Adebanwi, W. and Obadare, E. (2013) Introducing Nigeria at fifty: The nation in narration. In *Nigeria at Fifty* (pp. 1-28). Routledge.
- Afinotan, L.A. and Ojakorotu, V. (2014) Threat to Nigeria since 1960: A retrospection. *Canadian Social Science*, 10(5), pp.210-220.
- Afolabi, A., Ibem, E., Aduwo, E., Tunji-Olayeni, P. and Oluwunmi, O. (2019) Critical success factors (CSFs) for e-Procurement adoption in the Nigerian construction industry. *Buildings*, 9(2), p.47.
- Agénor, P.R. and da Silva, L.A.P. (2013) *Inflation targeting and financial stability: a perspective from the developing world*. Washington, DC: Inter-American Development Bank.
- Akinseinde, O.A. and Awolesi, J.A. (2015, September). The challenges and benefits of advance payment on the performance of Nigerian building contractors. In *The Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors: 2nd Research Conference-ReCon2 1st to 3rd September 2015* (p. 372).
- Alley, I. (2018) Oil price and USD-Naira exchange rate crash: Can economic diversification save the Naira?. *Energy Policy*, 118, pp.245-256.
- Alshboul, O., Shehadeh, A. and Hamedat, O. (2022) Governmental investment impacts on the construction sector considering the liquidity trap. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 38(2), p.04021099.
- Anowor, O.F. and Okorie, G.C. (2016) A reassessment of the impact of monetary policy on economic growth: Study of Nigeria. *International Journal of Developing and Emerging Economies*, 4(1), pp.82-90.
- Antal, M. and Van den Bergh, J.C. (2013) Macroeconomics, financial crisis and the environment: Strategies for a sustainability transition. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 6, pp.47-66.
- Auboin, M. and Ruta, M. (2013) The relationship between exchange rates and international trade: a literature review. *World Trade Review*, 12(3), pp.577-605.
- Baghebo, M. and Stephen, E.T. (2014) Monetary policy and economic growth in Nigeria (1980-2011). *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 4(1), p.20.
- Bailey, D.H., Duncan, G.J., Watts, T., Clements, D.H. and Sarama, J. (2018) Risky business: Correlation and causation in longitudinal studies of skill development. *American Psychologist*, 73(1), p.81.

- Bassey, G.E. and Essien, E.B. (2014) Inflation targeting framework for monetary policy in Nigeria: Issues, problems and prospects. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(12), pp.88-101.
- Bernanke, B.S. (2020) The new tools of monetary policy. *American Economic Review*, 110(4), pp.943-983.
- Borio, C.E. (2014) Monetary policy and financial stability: what role in prevention and recovery?.
- Ca'Zorzi, M., Dedola, L., Georgiadis, G., Jarocinski, M., Stracca, L. and Strasser, G. (2020) Monetary policy and its transmission in a globalised world.
- CBN (2017) Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Reports, 1 – 269.
- Chete, L.N., Adeoti, J.O., Adeyinka, F.M. and Ogundele, O. (2014) *Industrial development and growth in Nigeria: Lessons and challenges* (No. 2014/019). WIDER working paper.
- De Fiore, F., Hoerova, M. and Uhlig, H. (2018) *Money markets, collateral and monetary policy* (No. w25319). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Ebekozien, A., Ugochukwu, S.C. and Okoye, P.U. (2015) An analysis of the trends of foreign direct investment inflows in the Nigerian construction sector. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 5(1), pp.53-69.
- Ejem, C.A., Ogbonna, U.G. and Ogbudu, M.O. (2020) Response of Deposit Money Banks to Monetary Policy Dynamics in Nigeria. *Applied Economics and Finance*, 7(4), pp.33-47.
- Enweremadu, D.U. (2013) Nigeria as an emerging economy? Making sense of expectations. *South African Journal of International Affairs*, 20(1), pp.57-77.
- Falola, T. and Agbo, C. (2019) Nigeria. In *The Routledge Handbook to Religion and Political Parties* (pp. 29-310). Routledge.
- Gali, J. (2015) *Monetary policy, inflation, and the business cycle: an introduction to the new Keynesian framework and its applications*. Princeton University Press.
- Howden, D. (2013) The quantity theory of money.
- Idris, M. (2019) Monetary policy and economic growth in developing countries: evaluating the policy nexus in Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Economics Research*, 8(5), pp.290-300.
- Iheanacho, E. (2016) The contribution of government expenditure on economic growth of Nigeria disaggregated approach. *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 5(5), pp.1-8.
- Isa, R.B., Jimoh, R. and Achuen, E. (2013) An overview of the contribution of construction sector to sustainable development in Nigeria.
- Juhro, S.M. (2022) Central banking practices in the digital era: Salient challenges, lessons, and implications. *Central Bank Policy Mix: Issues, Challenges, and Policy Responses*, 261.
- Maida, C.A., Xiong, D., Marcus, M., Zhou, L., Huang, Y., Lyu, Y., Shen, J., Osuna-Garcia, A. and Liu, H. (2022) Quantitative data collection approaches in subject-reported oral health research: a scoping review. *BMC oral health*, 22(1), p.435.
- Mbusi, E. T. (2016) Influence of Monetary and Fiscal Policies on Construction output levels in Kenya, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, 1 – 125.
- Mfon, I. and Bassey, L. (2023) Sustainable Materials and Construction Practices in Industrial Buildings *International Journal of Developmental Studies and Environmental Monitoring* 2(1) Doi.10.6084/m9.figshare.2454870
- Mfon, I. and Etim, N. (2023). Harmonizing Aesthetics, Sustainability, and Post-Disaster Resilience: A Holistic Approach in Contemporary Architecture. *International Journal of Development, Sustainability and Environmental Management* 3(1) pp 15-20. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14873.80483
- Mirzaalian, F. and Halpenny, E. (2019) Social media analytics in hospitality and tourism: A systematic literature review and future trends. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 10(4), pp.764-790.
- Mudelsee, M. (2019) Trend analysis of climate time series: A review of methods. *Earth-science reviews*, 190, pp.310-322.

- NBS (2015) Nigerian Construction Sector Summary Report: 2010 – 2012, 1 – 15. Accessible from www.nigeranstat.gov.ng.
- Nwoko, N.M., IHEMEJE, J.C. and ANUMADU, E. (2016) The impact of monetary policy on the economic growth of Nigeria. *African Research Review*, 10(3), pp.192-206.
- Obioma, J. and Onyebueke, C. (2018) Bank asset quality performance among Nigerian banks-the role of monetary policy. *IIARD International Journal of Banking and Finance Research*, 4(1), pp.1-31.
- Olanrewaju, A.L., Abdul-Aziz, A.R., Olanrewaju, A.L. and Abdul-Aziz, A.R. (2015) An overview of the construction industry. *Building Maintenance Processes and Practices: The Case of a Fast Developing Country*, pp.9-32.
- Olanrewaju, O.I., Idiako, J.E. and Oyewobi, L.O. (2018) Global economic recession: Causes and effects on Nigeria building construction industry. *Journal of Surveying, Construction and Property*, 9(1), pp.9-18.
- Olotuase, S.O. (2014) A study of safety management in the Nigerian construction industry.
- Palley, T.I. (2015) Money, fiscal policy, and interest rates: A critique of Modern Monetary Theory. *Review of Political Economy*, 27(1), pp.1-23.
- Pivoňková, A. (2023) Real Estate as a Hedge against Inflation.
- Rostagno, M., Altavilla, C., Carboni, G., Lemke, W., Motto, R., Guilhem, A.S. and Yiangou, J. (2019) A tale of two decades: the ECB's monetary policy at 20.
- Rui, L., Sineviciene, L., Melnyk, L., Kubatko, O., Karintseva, O. and Lyulyov, O. (2019) Economic and environmental convergence of transformation economy: The case of China. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 17(3), pp.233-241.
- Sarstedt, M., Mooi, E., Sarstedt, M. and Mooi, E. (2019) Regression analysis. *A concise guide to market research: The process, data, and methods using IBM SPSS Statistics*, pp.209-256.
- Senthilnathan, S. (2019) Usefulness of correlation analysis. *Available at SSRN 3416918*.
- Smets, F. (2018) Financial stability and monetary policy: How closely interlinked? *35th issue (June 2014) of the International Journal of Central Banking*.

How to Cite this Work.

- Guobadia, J., Etim, N. and Mfon, I. (2024) The Impact of Monetary Policy Instruments on Nigeria's Construction Sector: A Focus on Money Supply, Inflation Rate, Exchange Rate, and Interest Rate. *International Journal of Development, Sustainability and Environmental Management* 4 (1) pp 1-15.

jenvironmentalmonitoring@gmail.com